

Enhancing maternal care: Applying the maternal near miss concept in intensive care units

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15343240>

Article Received: 20-March-2025, Revised: 10-April-2025, Accepted: 30-April-2025

ABSTRACT:

Background: The Maternal Near-Miss (MNM) concept, defined by WHO, identifies women who survive life-threatening obstetric complications. Its application in ICUs offers critical insights into maternal care quality. **Objective:** To evaluate maternal morbidity and outcomes among ICU-admitted obstetric patients using WHO MNM criteria. **Methods:** A retrospective study was conducted on 90 obstetric ICU admissions at MGM Medical College and Hospital, Aurangabad (Oct 2023–Oct 2024). Data on demographics, complications, interventions, and outcomes were analyzed. **Results:** MNM was observed in 62.2% of cases. Most patients were aged 21–25 years (46.7%) and admitted post-emergency caesarean section (50%). Severe pre-eclampsia (32.1%) and hemorrhage were leading causes. Blood transfusions (46.7%), ventilatory support (28.9%), and multidisciplinary care (57.8%) were key interventions. Maternal mortality was 2.2%. **Conclusion:** Applying the MNM approach in ICUs helps identify critical risk factors and improve maternal outcomes through timely, multidisciplinary care.

Keywords: *Maternal Near-Miss (MNM), WHO, ICU*

INTRODUCTION:

Maternal and child health is a key component of primary healthcare. While pregnancy is a natural process, it can often lead to life-threatening complications.[1] Maternal health is vital for the socio-economic development of communities, making it a priority of the Millennium Development Goals (MDG). Nearly 25% of global maternal deaths occur in India.[2] Maternal near-miss, defined by WHO as a woman who nearly died but survived a severe complication during pregnancy or childbirth serves as a critical tool for assessing obstetric care. [3] Identifying risk factors for near-miss events helps in planning preventive strategies to reduce maternal deaths. Major causes include hypertensive disorders, hemorrhage, sepsis, and obstructed labor. [4] MNM has similar characteristics and pathophysiological processes as maternal deaths [7]. While some women with severe acute complications die during pregnancy, childbirth or puerperium, a proportion of them narrowly escapes death. Analysis of “MNM” and maternal deaths is expected to facilitate assessment of the quality of obstetric care in health facilities and accessibility to reliable and objective data to reduce severe maternal morbidity and prevent maternal death. Demographic structural changes will not only increase the number of older women, but also heighten the

incidence and risks of complications and comorbidities of pregnancy and childbirth [12, 13]. Joint management of women with MNM by obstetricians and ICU-specialists is a major measure for the rescue of emergency obstetric care. Incidence of MNM in ICU can be used as an important indicator to judge lifethreatening obstetric complications [14]. A multi country survey by WHO showed that use of high-quality ICU is notably correlated with decline in MMR [15]. As a result, it is necessary to predict, identify and manage MNM admitted to ICU to improve risk prevention and control systems. [8]

Therefore, the present study was conducted to use the new WHO near-miss criteria to study maternal morbidity and mortality in a population of women with complications associated with pregnancy, childbirth or the postpartum period.

METHODS:

The present retrospective observational study based on the Maternal Near-Miss (MNM) concept was conducted amongst 90 Obstetric patients admitted to the ICU at MGM Medical College and Hospital, Aurangabad during October 2023 to October 2024.

Data Collection Tools: Patient medical records, WHO Maternal Near-Miss (MNM) criteria, Diagnostic reports

Data Points Collected: Age, obstetric history, gestational age, ICU admission types, complications

The study participants were the Women’s experiencing potentially life-threatening conditions during pregnancy, childbirth, or postnatal care. We analyzed the patient records to identify MNM cases following WHO guidelines. Data Analysis: Descriptive analysis and statistical comparisons on ICU admissions and MNM causes.

INCLUSION CRITERIA AND STUDY PROCEDURE:

RESULTS:

Table 1- Age Distribution of Patients:

Age in completed years	Number of patients (N=90)	Percentage
20 or less	12	13.33 %
21 to 25	42	46.66 %
26 to 30	16	17.77 %
31 to 35	12	13.33 %
More than 36	8	8.88 %
Total	90	100 %

Table no.1 shows that, the majority 42 (46.66 %) were form the age group of 21 – 25 years, followed by 16 (17.77%). There were only 8 (8.88%) above the age group of 36 years.

Table 2- ICU Admissions of Obstetric Patients

Timing of ICU admissions	Number of patients N=90)	Percentage
Antepartum	10	11.11 %
Postpartum		
Post Caesarean section		
Elective	20	22.22 %
Emergency	45	50.00 %
Post vaginal delivery	3	3.33 %
Ectopic	5	5.55 %
Abortion	7	7.77 %

Table no.2 shows that, 10 (11.11%) were admitted to ICU in Antepartum. While, majority 45(50%) were admitted post caesarean section in emergency and 20 (22.22%) were admitted post caesarean section electively. And 7 (7.77%) patients were admitted after abortion.

Table 3- Duration of ICU stay

Duration of ICU stay (Days)	Number of patients (N=90)	Percentage
1-2	26	28.88 %
3-4	38	42.22 %
5-10	20	22.22 %
>10	6	6.66 %

Table no.3 shows that the majority 38(42.22 %) of the patients were admitted in ICU for a period of 3 to4 days, followed by 20(22.22%) patients for 5 to 10 days. Only 6(6.66 %) patients required ICU for more than 10 days.

Table 4- Booking status

	Number of patients (N=90)	Percentage
Booked	38	42.22 %
Unbooked	52	57.77 %

Table no.4 shows that the majority 52 (57.77%) were Unbooked.

Table 5. Interventions used during the ICU stay

Particulars		Number of patients (N=90)	Percentage
Therapy given in ICU	Ventilator	26	28.88 %
	Inotropes	20	22.22 %
	Dialysis	2	2.22 %
Transfusion given	PCV	42	46.66 %
	Blood components	29	32.22 %
Multidisciplinary approach taken		52	57.77 %

Table no.5 shows that 42 (46.66 %) needed PCV, 29(32.22 %) needed other blood components, while 26(28.88 %) patients needed ventilatory support. While, in 52 (57.77%) cases multidisciplinary approach was taken.

Table 6: Determinants of Severe Maternal Morbidity, Near-Miss, and PLTC (Potentially Life-Threatening Conditions)

Determinants of severe maternal morbidity	PLTC (N=32)	Near-miss (N=56)	Death (N=2)
Hypertension (N=45)			
Eclampsia	4 (12.5 %)	6(10.71%)	-
Severe pre-eclampsia	7(21.87%)	18(32.14%)	-
HELLP	3(9.3%)	7(12.5%)	-
Haemorrhages (N=27)			
APH	1(3.1%)	1(1.78%)	-
Ectopic pregnancy	-	4(7.14%)	1(50.00%)
Adherent	-	-	1(50.00%)
Abortion	-	5(8.92%)	-
Uterine atony	2(6.25%)	11(19.64%)	-
Molar pregnancy	1(3.1%)	-	-
Infections (N=1)			
Sepsis	-	1(1.78%)	-
Others (N=17)			
Heart disease	9(28.12%)	1(1.78%)	-
Renal disease	2(6.25%)	-	-
Liver disease	-	1(1.78%)	-
GDM	1(3.1%)	1(1.78%)	-
Uterine mass	2(6.25%)	-	-

Table no.6 shows that

DISCUSSION:

The aim of the present study was to enhance maternal care by applying the Maternal Near-Miss (MNM) concept in Intensive Care Units (ICUs), with a focus on identifying critical risk factors and improving clinical practices to reduce maternal morbidity and mortality.

In the present study the majority 42 (46.66 %) were from the age group of 21 – 25 years, followed by 16 (17.77%). There were only 8 (8.88%) above the age group of 36 years.

Similarly Fa'tima Aparecida Lotufo(2012) found that the mean age of the women was 28.7 years (range 13-44 years).(7) In a study by Leonam Costa Oliveira(2015) found that the age of the participants was between 14 and 45 years, with a mean of 25.6 ± 6.99 years. (9)

In the present study, 10 (11.11%) were admitted to ICU in Antepartum. While, majority 45(50%) were admitted post caesarean section in emergency and 20 (22.22%) were admitted post caesarean section electively. And 7 (7.77%) patients were admitted after abortion.

In a study by Fa'tima Aparecida Lotufo(2012) found that majority of the patients were admitted to the ICU following delivery (138/158 cases, 87.3%). (7) Also, in a study by Ying Chen (2021) the percentage of caesarean birth in ICU (92.7%) was significantly higher than the overall 5-year cesarean birth rate in the hospital (46.1%). Most women with MNM ($n = 63$; 96.9%) were admitted in ICU postpartum. (8) Leonam Costa Oliveira (2015) in their study observed that the main disorders presented by the study participants were hypertension (62.7%), hemorrhage (53.7%), infections (49%), heart disease (4.7%), and thromboembolism (2.4%). Among the 160 cases of

hypertensive disorders, 108 (42.3%) were severe pre-eclampsia, 35 (13.7%) were eclampsia, and 17 (6.7%) were chronic hypertension exacerbated by pregnancy. One hundred five (41.2%) participants had HELLP syndrome. The most common infectious disorder was endometritis (25.1%), followed by pneumonia (19.6%) and sepsis, which occurred in 16.9% of patients. Regarding bleeding disorders, there were 90 (35.3%) cases of postpartum hemorrhage, 29 (11.4%) cases of placental abruption, and four cases of placental accreta. There were also cases of uterine rupture (three) and placenta previa (one). **(9) The above studies had similar findings to our study.**

In the present study, the majority 38(42.22 %) of the patients were admitted in ICU for a period of 3 to 4 days, followed by 20(22.22%) patients for 5 to 10 days. Only 6(6.66 %) patients required ICU for more than 10 days.

Similarly, Fa'tima Aparecida Lotufo(2012) found the length of hospital stay ranged from five to 86 days, averaging 14.8 ± 10.27 .**(9)**

Also, the mean ICU stay was 3.5 days (range 0-44 days), and 85.8% of the deliveries were performed by Caesarean section (121/141 deliveries). The total hospitalization time, the total time in the ICU, and the numbers of interventions and life support procedures, such as blood transfusions, were greater in the cases of near-miss and death was observed by Fa'tima Aparecida Lotufo(2012) . **(7)**

In the present study, 42 (46.66 %) patients needed PCV, 29(32.22 %) other blood components, while 26(28.88 %) patients needed ventilatory support. While, in 52 (57.77%) cases multidisciplinary approach was taken.

In a study by Ying Chen (2021) among the women admitted to the ICU, blood transfusion(≥ 5 units red blood cells), 15 received continuous administration of vasoactive drugs (dopamine/norepinephrine/epinephrine). Two women needed plasmapheresis, two renal dialysis, 24 endotracheal intubation and 34 non invasive assisted ventilation. Fourteen women were given continuous invasive blood pressure monitoring and because of large fluctuations of blood pressure and hypertensive crisis, 18 women had blood pressure monitoring by deep venipuncture. **(8)**

In the present study, majority near miss cases **18(32.14%) had** severe pre-eclampsia, while severe pre-eclampsia was seen in **7(21.87%) cases of PLTC. 11(19.64%) cases of** near miss had Uterine atony, while, **9(28.12%) cases of PLTC** had heart disease.

Fa'tima Aparecida Lotufo(2012) noted that the obstetrical complications were responsible for more than 80% of the ICU admissions in cases of PLTC; hypertensive conditions were the most common form of complication (67.7%). In cases of near-miss or

death, by contrast, the main factors involved were hemorrhagic complications in 39.5% of cases (17/43) and 40% of cases (2/5), respectively. Infections were reported in 17 cases, corresponding to an incidence of 1.75 per 1,000 live births and were classified as obstetrical in 3 cases and non obstetrical in 14 cases. **(7)**

In a study by Ying Chen (2021) observed that the overall, direct obstetric causes were the primary reasons for MNM (129/151; 85.4%). Leading direct obstetric causes of MNM in ICU were hypertensive disorders of pregnancy ($n = 24$; 36.9%) and postpartum hemorrhage ($n = 14$; 21.5%). The leading indirect obstetric cause of MNM admitted to the ICU was heart diseases ($n = 3$; 4.6%). Major cause of postpartum hemorrhage in both groups was both placenta accrete/ placenta previa ($n = 7$;10.8% in ICU and $n = 40$;46.4% outside ICU). **(8)**

In this study, hypertensive disorders, including severe pre-eclampsia and eclampsia, were significant contributors to maternal near-miss cases which is reflected in the total number of ICU admissions. Despite the high number of hypertensive cases, none of them led to deaths indicating better intrahospital care and appropriate interventions in adequate time frame. Both hemorrhages and caesarean section complications were key contributors to severe maternal morbidity in the present study. Hypertension was the main cause of admission and of potentially life-threatening conditions; however, hemorrhage was the main cause of maternal near-misses and deaths. Emergency caesarean sections, in particular, were associated with a higher risk of ICU admissions. In the present study, critical interventions in the ICU, such as blood transfusions, administration of magnesium sulphate, and the use of parenteral antibiotics, were vital in managing severe maternal complications.

CONCLUSION:

This study highlights the need for overall improvement in awareness among pregnant mothers and its timely accessibility with quality critical care management. Applying the maternal near-miss approach in ICUs can help reduce maternal mortality and morbidity. Near miss cases generally occur more frequently than maternal death and therefore a more reliable quantitative analysis can be carried out, which can provide more comprehensive profile of health system functioning.

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